

HAR-MI method for multi-class imbalanced datasets

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ABSTRACT

Research on multi-class imbalance from a number of researchers faces obstacles in the form of poor data diversity and a large number of classifiers. The Hybrid Approach Redefinition-Multiclass Imbalance (HAR-MI) method is a Hybrid Ensembles method which is the development of the Hybrid Approach Redefinition (HAR) method. This study has compared the results obtained with the Dynamic Ensemble Selection-Multiclass Imbalance (DES-MI) method in handling multiclass imbalance. In the HAR-MI Method, the preprocessing stage was carried out using the random balance ensembles method and dynamic ensemble selection to produce a candidate ensemble and the processing stages was carried out using different contribution sampling and dynamic ensemble selection to produce a candidate ensemble. This research has been conducted by using multi-class imbalance datasets sourced from the KEEL Repository. The results show that the HAR-MI method can overcome multi-class imbalance with better data diversity, smaller number of classifiers, and better classifier performance compared to a DES-MI method. These results were tested with a Wilcoxon signed-rank statistical test which showed that the superiority of the HAR-MI method with respect to DES-MI method.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Class imbalance occurs if a class or several classes become underrepresented so it is also called a minority class because it has instances that are much smaller than other classes [1]. In machine learning research, class imbalance problems are the main challenges that attract the attention of a number of researchers [2]. Research on this issue is included in the 20 main research topics that are the most interesting in machine learning, especially big data. Minority Class is also called a positive class because it is a class with interesting patterns to observe. For comparison, the detection of breast cancer sufferers is often a class with a small number of instances, if the classification process for detection of breast cancer sufferers experiences class imbalance problems then there is a possibility that detection of patients is not obtained even though the sufferer class is very interesting to obtain [3].

There are a number of methods that have been proposed to deal with class imbalance problems such as resampling, cost sensitive, ensemble learning, kernel-based methods, and active learning methods [4]. Multi-class imbalance problems are far more complicated to handle than two-class imbalances.

The multi-class imbalance condition will be more difficult if the desired results are as accurate as possible in accordance with the existing problem. On the other hand, applying the method proposed to handle two-class imbalance problems to handle multi-class imbalance problems does not get the desired results [5]. In general, the algorithm for handling multi-class imbalance is to develop an algorithm used for handling binary class Imbalance through the decomposition method [6]. Another common method is to adopt an ensemble-based approach for use in handling multi-class imbalances [4] and another way is to adapt the intrigue process by building decision trees [7]. A relatively easy way to do is to view multi-class imbalance as a subset of binary problems [8, 9].

The multi-class imbalance problems that will be solved are problems such as many minority-one majority, one minority-many majority, and many minority-many majority [10]. In [1] suggested that to overcome the problem of imbalance class there are 2 (two) things that need to be considered, namely those related to the number of classifiers and diversity (diversity) of data. In [11] propose the Dynamic Classifier Selection (DCS) method for dealing with multi-class imbalance problems, but it has the disadvantage of being a large number of classifiers. In [12] suggested the Dynamic Ensemble Selection (DES)-MI method which gives better results compared to the Dynamic Classifier Selection (DCS) method. The DES-MI method found has a small classifier, but in research conducted by [13] has identified that diversity data obtained by DES-MI is not good enough. The Hybrid Approach Redefinition (HAR) method which is a Hybrid Ensembles approach can overcome the problem of class imbalance with a small number of classifiers and good data diversity, on two-class imbalance problems [14, 15].

This research will optimize the HAR method so that it can be used to overcome multi-class imbalance problems. In the optimization process the preprocessing stages were carried out using the random balance ensemble method proposed by [16] and dynamic ensemble selection so that a candidate ensemble on multiclass problems and processing stages was carried out using different contribution sampling proposed by [17] and dynamic ensemble selection. This research will be conducted using multi-class imbalanced datasets sourced from the KEEL Repository [18]. The results of the study are the Hybrid Approach Redefinition-Multiclass Imbalance (HAR-MI) method that is expected to overcome multi-class imbalance with better data diversity, smaller number of classifiers, and better classifier performance compared to a DES-MI Method.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

This research will produce the HAR-MI method to overcome multi-class imbalance problems. HAR Method will be carried out an optimization process with HAR-MI method so that it can handle multi-class imbalance problems by adding capabilities from HAR method to determine candidate ensembles by using dynamic ensemble selection on minority classes and majority classes so that they can recognize each subset of minority and majority classes based on 2-Dimensional Datasets proposed by Sáez *et al.* [10]. The results of HAR-MI method are expected to obtain better data diversity and also a small number of classifiers. The stages of research conducted by researchers from this study can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Stages of research methods

In Figure 1, it can be seen that the process that occurs in the dataset selection and preparation stage is determined by the imbalance dataset with varying imbalance ratio. The next process is preprocessing. The process of handling the multi-class imbalance will begin with the preprocessing stage. The purpose of this preprocessing stage is to reduce the number of classifiers. Where the preprocessing stage will be done using the Random Balance Ensemble method and Dynamic Ensemble Selection. The Random Balance Ensemble Method will use Random under Sampling and SMOTEBoost. The results of the preprocessing stage are in the form of a preprocessing dataset which will then proceed to the processing stage. Implementation and validation of the performance of each experiment was carried out using 10-fold cross-validation and compared with the DES-MI method which is very good in dealing with multi-class imbalance problems.

2.1. Preprocessing and processing stage in HAR-MI method

The preprocessing stage was carried out using the Random Balance Ensembles Method and Dynamic Ensemble Selection. The pseudocode of this stage is as follows.

Require: Set S of examples (x_1, y_1)

Ensure: New set S' of examples with *Random Balance* and Dynamic Ensemble Selection

```

1:  $totalSize \leftarrow |S|$ 
2: Determine  $k$  as the number of Nearest Neighbor
3: For All Samples in  $S$  do
4:   Determine the Borderline of Positive or Minority Class as  $E_oC_t^+$ 
5:   Determine the Borderline of Negative or Majority Class as  $E_oC_t^-$ 
6: End For
7: For All Samples in  $E_oC_t^+$  do
8:   Calculate the  $cn(e)_i$  as neighborhood value for each sample
9:   Order Ascending the sample according to the  $cn(e)_i$ 
10: End For
11: Building a candidate ensemble for Safe, Borderline, Rare, dan Outlier according to  $k$  value
12: Take a candidate ensemble of Safe, Borderline, Rare, dan Outlier to  $SP$ 
13: For All Samples in  $E_oC_t^-$  do
14:   Take a candidate ensemble to  $SN$ 
15: End For
16: Add Instance from with  $S|y_i=+1$  to  $S_P$ 
17: Add Instance from with  $S|y_i=-1$  to  $S_N$ 
18: Calculate the size of Majority Class from  $S_N$ 
19: Calculate the size of Majority Class from  $S_P$ 
20:  $newMajoritySize \leftarrow$  Random integer between 2 and  $totalSize-2$ 
21:  $newMinoritySize \leftarrow totalSize - newMajoritySize$  8: if  $newMajoritySize$ 
22: if  $newMajoritySize < majoritySize$  then
23:    $S' \leftarrow S_P$ 
24:    $S'$  will fill with a random instance from  $S_N$ 
25:   Create  $newMinoritySize - minoritySize$  artificial
26: else
27:    $S' \leftarrow S_N$ 
28:    $S'$  will fill with a random instance from  $S_P$ 
29:   create  $newMajoritySize - majoritySize$  artificial
30: end if
31: return  $S'$ 

```

Based on the pseudocode above, it can be seen that in the preprocessing stage was carried out using Random Under Sampling and SMOTEBoost. In the Random Under Sampling process the Dynamic Ensemble Selection process will take the form of borderline determination for minority and majority class. Then for samples that are in the borderline minority class $E_oC_t^+$, the neighborhood value calculation process $cn(e)$ will be performed, then it will be sorted ascending to determine the candidate ensemble for Safe, Borderline, Rare, and Outlier, then the candidate ensemble will be included in the SP . Next for the sample that is in the borderline the major class will be entered into SN .

After that, the process will continue with the Random Balance Ensemble Method, which will be based on the results of the Dynamic Ensemble Selection. The process starts with the determination of Majority and Minority Size. Then based on the determination of the size, an imbalance class will be handled.

If the size of the new Majority Class is greater than the new Majority Class, this means that the Minority Class is larger than the Majority Class and part of the Minority Class instance will be taken to move to the Majority Class and vice versa. Determination of the sample will be done by Random Under Sampling and the determination of the instance that will be transferred will be done with SMOTEBoost. The Processing stages was carried out using the Different Contribution Sampling and Dynamic Ensemble Selection. The pseudocode of this stage is as follows.

```

1: Input:  $S$ : Training Set;  $T$ : Number of Iterations;  $n$ : Bootstrap Size;  $k$ : neighbors
2: Output: Bagged Classifier:  $H(x) = \text{sign}(\sum_{t=1}^T h_t(x))$  where  $h_t[-1, 1]$  are the induced classifiers
3: Process:
4: For All Samples in  $S$  do
5:   Determine the Borderline of Positive or Minority Class as  $EoC_t^+$ 
6:   Determine the Borderline of Negative or Majority Class as  $EoC_t^-$ 
7: End For
8: For All Samples in  $EoC_t^+$  do
9:   Calculate the  $cn(e)$ ; as neighborhood value for each sample
10:  Order Ascending the sample according to the  $cn(e)_i$ 
11: End For
12: Building a candidate ensemble for Safe, Borderline, Rare, dan Outlier according to  $k$  value
13: Take a candidate ensemble of Safe, Borderline, Rare, dan Outlier to  $SP$ 
14: For All Samples in  $EoC_t^-$  do
15:   Take a candidate ensemble to SN
16: End For
17: for  $i = 1$  to Number of Instance in Preprocessed Dataset do
18:   Add Preprocessed Dataset to  $S_i$ 
19:   B-SVM will do for classifying  $S_i$ 
20:   Determine the Majority Class
21:   Determine the Minority Class
22:   For All Instance in Majority Class do
23:     NewSVSets[] will form by checking and delete the noise in SV Sets
24:     NewNSVSets[] will form by multiple RUS
25:   end while
26:   For All instance from new SV Sets and NSV do
27:     Create an instance for Majority Class
28:   End For
29:   For All Instance in Minority Class do
30:     SMOTEBoost Process for SV Sets and create SMOTESets
31:   end while
32:   For All SMOTESets and NewNSVSets do
33:     New PositiveSampleSets
34:   End For
35:   For All NewNegativeSampleSets and NewPositiveSampleSets do
36:     ResultDataSet
37:   End For
38: End For

```

After the preprocessing dataset is generated, the Dynamic Ensemble Selection process will occur at the initial stage for borderline determination of minority and majority class. Then the next step will be the Differential Contribution Sampling process where both majority classes and minority classes will be divided into SV Sets and NSV Sets. NSV Sets in the Negative Sample will undergo a Multiple RUS process, while SV Sets in the Positive Sample will experience a SMOTEBoost.

2.2. Data diversity

In the ensemble learning process, in reality if there is a classifier that can guarantee that there is no misclassification, an ensemble process is not needed on the classifier. The ensemble process in the classifier occurs in the hope that better results can be obtained. Assuming that if there is a misclassification of the classifier in a part it can be covered by merging with other classifiers that also misclassification in other parts [19].

According to Díez-Pastor, Rodríguez, García-Osorio, and Kuncheva [16] it is important to pay attention to the diversity of data in handling imbalance classes. This means that attempted misclassification produced by each classifier is as small as possible and if there is misclassification it is expected to occur on different objects or parts [20]. Suppose that $Z = \{z_1, \dots, z_n\}$ which is a dataset that is in the decision region \mathfrak{R}^n , so that $z_j \in \mathfrak{R}^n$ it is an instance involved in the classification problem. Then the output of the classifier D_i as a classifier paired comparison matrix (relationship pairwise classifier) can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Relationship pairwise classifier matrix [20]

	D_k Correct (1)	D_k Wrong (0)
D_i Correct (1)	N^{11}	N^{10}
D_i Wrong (0)	N^{01}	N^{00}

Diversity data can be calculated using Q-Statistics [21].

$$Q_{i,k} = \frac{N^{11}N^{00} - N^{01}N^{10}}{N^{11}N^{00} + N^{01}N^{10}} \quad (1)$$

2.3. Classifier

Classifiers can generally be defined as *Decision Region* \mathfrak{R}^n that place an object into a set *class* Ω , where Ω consists of class $\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_n$. This can be seen in (9) [20].

$$D: \mathfrak{R}^n \rightarrow \Omega \quad (2)$$

Where D is the classifier and is the set of each point in the decision region \mathfrak{R}^i which is intended for *class* ω_i .

2.4. Classifier performance

ROC Curve is one statistical method that is often used to determine the performance of a classifier. This curve is generated by plotting the true positive fraction of a positive sample in the Y axis with the false positive fraction of a negative sample (False Positive Rate) in the X axis [22]. The concepts of True Positive and False Positive can be seen in the Confusion Matrix as can be seen in Table 2 [23].

Table 2. Confusion matrix [24]

	Classified as positive	Classified as negative
Positive samples	<i>True Positive</i> (TP)	<i>False Negative</i> (FN)
Negative samples	<i>False Positive</i> (FP)	<i>True Negative</i> (TN)

The number of performance classifier measurement parameters in the two class problems are as follows [25].

$$TPrate = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3)$$

$$FPrate = \frac{FP}{TN + FP} \quad (4)$$

$$TNrate = \frac{TN}{TN + FP} \quad (5)$$

$$Recall = TPrate \quad (6)$$

$$Precision = PPValue = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (7)$$

$$F-Measure = \frac{2RP}{R+P} \quad (8)$$

$$G-Mean = \sqrt{TPrate \cdot TNrate} \quad (9)$$

True Positive Rate (TPRate) is stated as a recall which states the percentage of data captured is relevant data. Positive Predictive Value (PPValue) is stated as Precision which states the percentage of relevant data identified to be taken. F-Measure states the harmonic average value between recall and precision. The F-Measure value is usually smaller than 2, the higher the value of F-Measure states that both recall and precision are quite high. G-Means on the other hand states the balance between positive samples and negative samples [23]. Performance measurement in multi class imbalance is basically a modification of two class problems, and in general there are 2 (two) parameters used, namely: *MAvA* and *MFm* [26].

$$MAvA = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N ACC_i}{m} \quad (10)$$

where m is the number of classes and ACC_i stands for the accuracy rate for the class I and $MAvA$ is the average value of accuracy.

$$MFm = \frac{F - measure_i}{m} \quad (11)$$

where MFm is the multi-class F-Measure.

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1. Dataset description

This study uses a multi-class imbalanced dataset that is sourced from the KEEL Repository. The dataset selected in this study has represented a low, medium and high imbalance ratio. For datasets with a low imbalance ratio are Balance Scale datasets, datasets with moderate imbalance ratio are Car Evaluation datasets, and dataset with high imbalance ratio are Red Wine Quality datasets, Ecoli, and Pageblocks. Dataset description can be seen in Table 3 [18].

Table 3. Dataset description[18]

Dataset	#Ex	#Atts	Distribution of class	IR
Balance scale	625	4	288/49/288	5.88
Car evaluation	1728	6	384/69/1210/65	18.62
Red wine quality	1599	11	10/53/681/638/199/18	68.1
Ecoli	336	7	2/2/5/20/35/52/77/143	71.5
Pageblocks	548	10	3/8/12/33/492	164

3.2. Testing result

The first test is to obtain a comparison of the number of classifier and diversity data obtained by using HAR-MI and DES-MI method. Testing of each method will be carried out as many as 10 testing for each dataset. The average test results can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4. Testing result for number of classifier and data diversity for each method

Dataset	HAR-MI method		DES-MI method	
	Number of Classifier	Data Diversity (Q-Statistics)	Number of Classifier	Data Diversity (Q-Statistics)
Balance scale	191.6	0.397	197.2	0.421
Car evaluation	471.6	0.457	487.9	0.461
Red wine quality	397.8	0.431	395.3	0.411
Ecoli	91.1	0.397	121.2	0.413
Pageblocks	117.8	0.441	119.6	0.456

Based on the results in Table 4, it can be seen that HAR-MI Method gives better results on better data diversity in the three datasets when compared with DES-MI Method. The test results for the HAR-MI method classifier are better in the Balance Scale, Car Evaluation, Ecoli, and Pageblocks datasets. For the Red Wine Quality dataset, DES-MI is slightly superior compared to HAR-MI. There is a tendency if the number of attributes increases, the sampling process, especially on Random Under Sampling, requires a larger

classifier. However, the difference in the number of classifiers is not very significant. The results of testing *MAvA* and *MFm* can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5. Testing Result for *MAvA* and *MFm* for Each Method

Dataset	HAR-MI method		DES-MI method	
	<i>MAvA</i>	<i>MFm</i>	<i>MAvA</i>	<i>MFm</i>
Balance scale	66.71	0.71	61.29	0.61
Car evaluation	97.68	0.97	94.27	0.945
Red wine quality	45.24	0.43	41.81	0.395
Ecoli	57.31	0.58	49.67	0.51
Pageblocks	47.81	0.49	45.92	0.44

In Table 5 it can be seen that HAR-MI Method gives better results for *MAvA* and *MFm* when compared to DES-MI Method. Both methods have provided excellent *MAvA* and *MFm* values. A good *MAvA* means that the accuracy of the classification has been very good, where the misclassification that occurs is very minimal. This means that the instance of the minority class has been classified correctly and also the majority class instances that are incorrectly classified as minority classes are also minimal. This is because F-Measure states how many instances in the minority class are correctly defined and also measures how many instances in the majority class are incorrectly classified as minority classes.

3.2. Testing result

The statistical test is performed using the Wilcoxon signed-rank test which is a statistical procedure to measure performance based on pairwise comparison [27]. Wilcoxon tests are carried out to compare the performance of the HAR-MI method with the DES-MI method using *MAvA* and *MFm*. The results obtained can be seen in Table 6.

Table 6. Wilcoxon signed-rank test for comparing performance measurements using *MAvA* and *MFm*

Performance measurement	P-Value	Hypothesis
<i>MAvA</i>	0.043114	H_0 (no significant score difference between HAR-MI and DES-MI) is rejected and this means H_1 (there is a significant difference between HAR-MI and DES-MI in score) is Accepted because the p-value <0.05
<i>MFm</i>	0.043114	H_0 (no significant score difference between HAR-MI and DES-MI) rejected and this means H_1 (there is a significant difference between HAR-MI and DES-MI in score) Accepted because the p-value <0.05

Based on the results of testing with the Wilcoxon signed-rank test that can be seen in Table 6, there is a significant difference between HAR-MI and DES-MI and this indicates that the superiority of the HAR-MI method.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the test results it can be seen that HAR-MI method gives better results compared to DES-MI method for both the number of classifier, data diversity, and also the performance classifier. It should be noted that for the number of classifiers, where if the dataset has many attributes such as the Red Wine Quality, then the HAR-MI method can produce poor results. In general, the imbalance ratio does not have a significant effect on the test results. This means that both HAR-MI method and DES-MI method can handle the imbalance problem class very well. Future research, it is expected that HAR-MI method can be optimized so that it can be applied to datasets for a large number of attributes without causing a large number of classifiers. The main attention needs to be given to the sampling method used in the HAR-MI method. It is necessary to find another sampling alternative at the preprocessing and processing stages.

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